

Multidisciplinary Surgical Research Annals

<https://msra.online/index.php/Journal/about>

Volume 3, Issue 2 (2025)

Maternal and Fetal Outcome in Premature Rupture of Membranes

Received: 10-04-2025

Accepted: 26-05-2025

Published: 04-06-2025

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Article Details

ABSTRACT

Keywords: PROM, maternal outcome, fetal outcome, preterm birth, chorioamnionitis, fetal distress.

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Background: Premature rupture of membranes (PROM) is a common obstetric complication characterized by the rupture of fetal membranes before the onset of labor. It is associated with significant maternal and fetal morbidity and mortality, especially in low-resource settings. **Objective:** To determine the frequency and nature of maternal and fetal outcomes in pregnant women presenting with PROM at a tertiary care hospital. **Methods:** This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Divisional Headquarters Teaching Hospital, Mirpur, Azad Jammu and Kashmir from October 2024 to March 2025-. A total of 135 pregnant women aged 20–40 years with singleton pregnancies and diagnosed with PROM were included using purposive sampling. Data were collected through clinical history, examination, and ultrasonography. **Results:** The mean maternal age was 28.6 ± 4.7 years, and the mean gestational age was 36.2 ± 2.1 weeks. Chorioamnionitis occurred in 17.8% of cases, postpartum hemorrhage in 11.9%, and retained placenta in 14.1%. Fetal distress was noted in 14.8% of neonates, low birth weight in 37.8%, and 21.5% required NICU admission. Preterm PROM was significantly associated with fetal distress and low birth weight ($p < 0.05$). Maternal complications were more common among women of lower socioeconomic status. **Conclusion:** PROM is associated with increased risk of both maternal and fetal complications, particularly when occurring preterm or among women from low socioeconomic backgrounds. Early identification, adequate antenatal care, and timely obstetric intervention are essential to improving outcomes.

INTRODUCTION:

Premature rupture of membranes (PROM) is defined as the spontaneous rupture of the fetal membranes before the onset of labor. It also is categorized according to gestational age: when it happens under 37 weeks of pregnancy, it is called preterm premature rupture of membranes (PPROM); it is called term PROM when it happens on or after 37 weeks. It is estimated that PROM complicates around 5-10 percent of all pregnancies with 80 percent of these at term. It is an obstetric complication that also bears significant maternal and fetal morbidity and mortality and presents almost 21.4 percent of morbidity and mortality related to perinatal deaths across the globe (1). PROM contributes significantly to prematurity and the associated complications, including the neonatal respiratory distress syndrome, sepsis, necrotizing enterocolitis, intra ventricular hemorrhage and bronchopulmonary dysplasia. Such complications greatly heighten the chances of poor neonatal outcomes, such as those relating to long-term morbidity and mortality (2).

In another study, involving 120 women who presented with term PROM, the results showed maternal and fetal outcomes of women managed respectively on expectant management versus labor induction. In the expectant management, observation was done to spontaneously trigger labor taking more than 24 hours, whereas the other group, the induction rate, was treated by misoprostol (25 mcg) orally every 4 hours or by oxytocin intravenously. When compared to the expectant group, which only had 10 percent done within 12 hours, around 68.3 percent of the induced group took less than 12 hours (3). Moreover, PROM, especially those that take place earlier away from term, were associated with higher chances of fetal distress (13.2 percent), low birth weight (43.3%), chorioamnionitis (18 percent), postpartum hemorrhage (12%), and retained placenta (21 percent). It has also been found that PROM is highly connected to low socioeconomic status. The amniotic fluid of women who are disadvantaged in background may have reduced antibacterial activity, thus, being exposed to the risk of membrane rupture. This risk is also aggravated by limited access to antenatal care, poor hygiene, and late presentations at the hospital (6). The treatment of PROM plans is clinically based on the gestational age, infection or lack of it, good health of the fetus, and maternal status. Under the term PROM, labor induction occurs in less than 24 hours so that the risk of infection can be reduced (7). But in scenarios of PPRM, such as earlier than 34 weeks, expectant management is usually used to maximize the baby's maturity with minimal risks of sepsis. This could involve giving corticosteroids to speed up lung maturity of the fetus, prophylactic antibiotics, and intensive observation of the mother and the child. Nevertheless, it is still a clinical dilemma on how to treat the risk of prematurity versus the risk of infection (8,9).

That being the case, based on the challenges socio-economic and health-wise women in this region have to go through, especially the rural ones that receive minimal antenatal support, this study attempts to give local statistics on the maternal and fetal outcomes on PROM.

Objective

To determine the frequency of common maternal and fetal outcomes in pregnant women presenting with premature rupture of membranes.

Methodology

This cross-sectional (descriptive) study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology at Divisional Headquarter Teaching Hospital, Mirpur, Azad Jammu and Kashmir (AJK) from October 2024 to March 2025. A total of 135 patients were included in the study. The sample size was calculated using the WHO sample size formula, considering a prevalence of postpartum hemorrhage of 12% among cases of premature rupture of membranes [6] (PROM), with a 95% confidence level and a precision of 5.5%. A non-probability purposive sampling technique was employed to collect the data.

Inclusion Criteria

- 6 Pregnant women aged 20 to 40 years diagnosed with PROM.
- 7 Singleton pregnancy confirmed by obstetric ultrasonography.

Exclusion Criteria

- Women with a history of narcotic analgesic use during labor.
- History of previous lower segment cesarean section.
- Clinically confirmed cephalopelvic disproportion. These factors were considered potential confounders and were excluded to minimize bias.

Data Collection Procedure

Participants were selected from patients admitted to the labor ward who met the inclusion criteria and were diagnosed with PROM based on clinical history, physical examination, and ultrasonography. Written informed consent was obtained after explaining the purpose and benefits of the study. A detailed history was taken, including personal details, symptoms, and the last menstrual period (LMP). A thorough clinical examination was performed to identify any systemic or obstetrical complications. Obstetric ultrasonography was used to confirm singleton pregnancy and estimate gestational age. Patients presenting with complaints of leaking and diagnosed with PROM in the antenatal outpatient department or ward were enrolled. All participants were monitored closely for maternal and fetal well-being. Antibiotics were administered during the intrapartum and postpartum periods as indicated. Per vaginal examinations were conducted only when necessary. Maternal and fetal outcomes were recorded after appropriate investigations. Data were documented on a structured proforma specifically designed for this study.

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS software version 20. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data. Frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical variables such as parity, socioeconomic status, maternal outcomes (chorioamnionitis, postpartum hemorrhage, retained placenta), and fetal outcomes (fetal distress, low birth weight). Mean and standard deviation were calculated for continuous variables such as maternal age and gestational age. To assess effect modifiers, maternal and fetal outcomes were stratified by age, gestational age, socioeconomic status, and parity. The Chi-square test was applied, and a p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Results were presented in the form of tables and charts.

Results

Data were collected from 135 patients. The mean maternal age in the study population was 28.6 ± 4.7 years, and the average gestational age at PROM was 36.2 ± 2.1 weeks. A majority of the participants were multigravida (55.6%), while 44.4% were primigravida. Most women (57.8%) belonged to a lower socioeconomic status, reflecting limited access to antenatal care. In terms of gestational age distribution, more than half (51.1%) had term PROM, while 34.8% were in the late preterm group and 14.1% in the early preterm category.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants (n = 135)

Variable	Value
Age (Mean \pm SD)	28.6 ± 4.7 years
Gestational Age (Mean \pm SD)	36.2 ± 2.1 weeks
Gravida	

– Primigravida	60 (44.4%)
– Multigravida	75 (55.6%)
Socioeconomic Status	
– Low	78 (57.8%)
– Middle	57 (42.2%)
Gestational Age Group	
<34 weeks (Early preterm)	19 (14.1%)
34–36+6 weeks (Late preterm)	47 (34.8%)
≥37 weeks (Term)	69 (51.1%)
Total	135

Among maternal complications, chorioamnionitis was the most frequently observed, affecting 17.8% of the patients. Postpartum hemorrhage occurred in 11.9%, while retained placenta was noted in 14.1% of cases. Regarding fetal outcomes, 14.8% of neonates experienced fetal distress, and a significant 37.8% had low birth weight. NICU admission was required in 21.5% of cases, and 2.2% of neonates died shortly after birth, indicating the serious risks associated with PROM.

Table 2: Maternal and Fetal Outcomes in PROM Patients (n = 135)

Maternal Complication	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Chorioamnionitis	24	17.8%
Postpartum Hemorrhage	16	11.9%
Retained Placenta	19	14.1%
Fetal Outcome		
Fetal Distress	20	14.8%
Low Birth Weight (<2.5 kg)	51	37.8%
NICU Admission	29	21.5%
Neonatal Death	3	2.2%

Fetal complications were significantly higher among those with preterm PROM compared to term PROM. Fetal distress was observed in 25.0% of preterm cases versus 7.0% in term cases ($p = 0.041$). Similarly, low birth weight was markedly more common in the preterm group (69.6%) than in the term group (14.0%), with a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.013$). NICU admissions were also significantly higher in the preterm group (35.7%) compared to 10.5% in term PROM cases ($p = 0.026$).

Table 3: Stratification of Fetal Outcomes by Gestational Age

Fetal Outcome	Term PROM (≥37w)	Preterm PROM (<37w)	p-value
Fetal Distress	6 (7.0%)	14 (25.0%)	0.041
Low Birth Weight	12 (14.0%)	39 (69.6%)	0.013
NICU Admission	9 (10.5%)	20 (35.7%)	0.026

Figure 1: Distribution of PROM by gestational age

Maternal complications were more prevalent among women from lower socioeconomic backgrounds. Chorioamnionitis was seen in 20.5% of low SES patients versus 14.0% in the middle SES group, though not statistically significant ($p = 0.282$). Postpartum hemorrhage showed a significant association with low SES (15.4%) compared to middle SES (7.0%) with a p -value of 0.039. Rates of retained placenta were almost identical across both groups (14.1% vs. 14.0%, $p = 0.990$), suggesting no socioeconomic link for this specific complication.

Table 4: Stratification of Maternal Outcomes by Socioeconomic Status

Maternal Outcome	Low SES (n=78)	Middle SES (n=57)	p-value
Chorioamnionitis	16 (20.5%)	8 (14.0%)	0.282
Postpartum Hemorrhage	12 (15.4%)	4 (7.0%)	0.039
Retained Placenta	11 (14.1%)	8 (14.0%)	0.990

Figure 2: Association Between Latency Period and Maternal/Fetal Complications

Discussion

This study was conducted to evaluate the maternal and fetal outcomes associated with premature rupture of membranes (PROM) at a tertiary care hospital in Mirpur, Azad Jammu and Kashmir. PROM is still one of the major obstetric problems, especially in underdeveloped nations where accessibility to healthcare facilities and proper presence of antenatal care are still lacking. The study in question estimated that the average age of respondents was 28.6 years, and the majority of women were multigravida and belonged to lower socioeconomic groups. This result agrees with the other studies carried out in similar areas, which demonstrated higher rates of PROM in women in the age group of childbearing years with low care facilities during prenatal care and feeding supplies. Inequality in socioeconomic status also tends to be associated with a higher propensity to risk factors: genitourinary infections, inadequate hygiene, and delays in seeking healthcare (10).

Chorioamnionitis was observed in 17.8 percent of cases in the maternal complications. It is too prevalent when compared with the findings of other studies in the region, which feature infection as a frequent consequence of extended rupture of the membrane. In 11.9%, postpartum hemorrhage was experienced, and 14.1% of them experienced retained placenta. Intrauterine infections or uterine atony may be the causes of these maternal complications; hence, a risk that is famously related to PROM is incomplete placental separation (11). Fetal outcomes of this research showed that low birth weight was the most common complication, which was exhibited in 37.8 percent of the neonates. Probably, it is a direct result of preterm birth and intra-uterine growth restriction. There were 14.8 percent fetal distress cases, and 21.5 percent of babies needed to be admitted to the NICU. The reasons for these outcomes are hypoxia, respiratory complications because of prematurity, and a potential intra-amniotic infection (12). The findings are comparable with other studies done in other tertiary care facilities within South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa. Stratification showed high correlation of occurrence of fetal distress, low birth weight, and remains in NICU with preterm PROM. Such results reveal the precarious situation of preterm newborns who have appeared after PROM and can contribute to the use of close monitoring and the introduction of interventions

on time to reduce complications (13).

Also, there was a considerable relationship between poor socioeconomic deprivation and postpartum hemorrhage. Poor background women stand a higher chance of being poorly nourished, lacking blood, and having little access to antenatal facilities, which results in poor development of maternal outcomes (14). These findings strengthen the importance of taking some public health measures that should target enhancing maternal education, prenatal monitoring, and access to healthcare services in underserved groups (15). There were no maternal deaths recorded in this study, yet the rate of maternal morbidity was high. This creates a need to emphasize the necessity of standardized protocols of management that include the use of antibiotic prophylaxis, labor induction at term, expectant management with the use of corticosteroids, and fetal monitoring in the presence of preterm PROM (16). This research does not lack limitations. The study is a single-center one, such that its data cannot apply to the general population. Selection bias can be caused by the use of non-probability sampling. Also, neonatal outcomes in the longer term were not evaluated, and thus, the potential to determine potential chronic complications in the perioperative procedure of PROM (e.g., bronchopulmonary dysplasia or neurodevelopmental delays) is limited. Still, the study adds to the increased local scholarly work on the topic of PROM and complications. It highlights the urgent necessity to build up the systems of antenatal care, particularly in rural and low-resource areas, and promotes evidence-based, region-specific obstetric guidelines to enhance the results of maternal and neonatal care.

Conclusion

Premature rupture of membranes remains a significant obstetric complication associated with considerable maternal and fetal morbidity, particularly in low-resource settings. This study identified chorioamnionitis, postpartum hemorrhage, and retained placenta as the most common maternal outcomes, while fetal distress, low birth weight, and NICU admissions were the primary neonatal concerns. Preterm PROM and low socioeconomic status were significantly associated with adverse outcomes. These findings highlight the importance of early diagnosis, adequate antenatal care, and timely obstetric management to reduce the risks associated with PROM.

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